

Populism and The Prospects of Clash of Civilization in Contemporary Global Politics: An Analysis

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ABSTRACT: This paper is set to critically examine the extent to which the existence of populism accentuates the prospect of clash of civilization. To achieve this, the paper employed content analysis to x-ray the interplay between populist movements and civilizational narratives and how this interplay accentuates the prospect of clash of civilization. The paver found that Populism, with its divisive rhetoric and emphasis on identity politics, has emerged as a significant force in shaping contemporary global dynamics and has accentuates he prospects of a Clash of Civilizations as theorized by Samuel P. Huntington. The paper revealed how populist leaders exploit cultural and religious identities to frame conflicts as inherent and irreconcilable. The use of "us versus them" rhetoric exacerbates civilizational divides, fuelling tensions on issues such as migration, globalization, and national sovereignty. The paper concludes that the existence of populism serves as both a reflection of and a catalyst for the tens Ions predicted by the Clash of Civilizations thesis. It amplifies civilizational divides by fostering exclusionary identities and antagonistic rhetoric, heightening the risk of cultural and geo-political conflicts. To counter these dynamics, the paper recommended among others that governments and leaders should prioritize inclusive governance that addresses the concerns of diverse groups within their societies. The findings underscore the urgent need for addressing populist grievances and fostering mutual understanding to prevent the entrenchment of cultural divides end ensure a more stable and cooperative international order.

KEYWORDS: Populism, Civilization, Clash of Civilization, Global Politics

INTRODUCTION

In the last few decades, the political landscape across the globe has been dramatically reshaped by the rise of populist movements, challenging traditional political establishments and igniting intense debates about the future of democracy, sovereignty, and global cooperation. In other words, the rise of populism in contemporary political landscapes with its focus on appealing to the common people and often rejecting elites and established political systems, has gained significant traction in both Western and non-Western societies and thereby becoming a central locus at academic and public discourse.

Over the past few decades, populist movements have proliferated across various regions, reflecting a widespread disillusionment with traditional political elites and institutions! These movements often capitalize on existing societal economic inequality, cultural change, and perceived threats to nation typically frame their political agendas around the traditional values, and cultural homogeneity, positioning themselves as protectors of a "pure" national culture against foreign-influences. They also tend to frame political struggles as battles between "us" (the people) and "them" (the elites, immigrants, or foreign powers).

In Europe, for example, the rise of populism has been strongly tied to concerns over immigration, especially from Muslim-majority countries. Leaders like Marine Le Pen of France Geert Wilders in the Netherlands, and Matteo Salvini in Italy have rallied against what they perceive as the erosion of Western Christian culture due to the influx of refugees and migrants, particularly following the European migrant crisis of 2015. These populist figures have used rhetoric that positions their national identities as fundamentally at odds with the cultures of those seeking asylum, reinforcing cultural divides that Huntington argued would be the source of future conflict (De-Cueto-Nogueras, (2018).

In the United States, the Trump's "America First" agenda, his strong opposition to 'immigration from predominantly Muslim and Latin American countries, and his critique of Multilateral institutions such as the United Nations and NATO reflects a populist worldview that prioritizes national sovereignty and cultural purity. This is to say that Trump's rhetoric political agenda was framed on the need to "protect American culture" from the perceived threats of globalization and immigration. This also to some extent resonates with Huntington's argument that civilizations with distinct cultural identities may find themselves in conflict as they interact more globally.

Moreover, in countries such as India and Brazil as pointed out by Santana, and Ferrario, (2022), populist leaden like Narendra Modi and Jair Bolsonaro have used nationalist and cultural rhetoric to galvanize their political bases. Modi, for instance, has employed Hindu nationalist rhetoric, positioning India's identity as rooted Hindu culture, while simultaneously criticizing the

Muslim minority population as a threat to India's cultural fabric. Similarly, Bolsonaro's rise to power in Brazil as argued by Løland, (2020) was marked by strong appeals to Brazilian nationalism and traditional values, particularly his alignment with evangelical Christianity and his opposition to progressive social movement.

Therefore, we can opine from the above premises that the growing prominence of populist rhetoric, especially in Europe, the United States, and parts of Asia has often been accompanied by heightened fears of cultural and religious differences. These fears as observed above have been further exacerbated by global migration, the rise of Non-Western powers such as China, and conflicts in the Middle East, which have led to a resurgence of cultural fault lines and thereby inadvertently or deliberately heighten the tensions between different civilizations, making the possibility of a "clash" more likely.

Although some scholars and commentators have argued that the relationship between populism and the clash of civilizations is not necessarily linear or predetermined, we can deduce from the foregoing that, as populist leaders across the world increasingly invoke nationalist, religious, and cultural rhetoric, the prospect of conflicts between different civilizations appears to be intensifying. This paper therefore is set to critically explore how the rise or existence of populism in contemporary global politics accentuates the prospect and potential for a clash of civilizations as postulated by political scientist Samuel Huntington in the early 1990s.

To achieve this, the following question' is pertinent to ask: In what ways populism or populist movements amplify cultural and civilizational divides? In other words, how the rise or existence of populism in contemporary global politics accentuates the prospect for a clash of civilizations as postulated by Samuel Huntington in the early 1990s? Attempt is made to provide answers to this question in the subsequent section of this work.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The central theme of this paper revolves around some key concepts that require a brief discussion in order to have clear focus. These conceptual terms are:

Populism is a range of political stances that emphasize the idea of the common 'people and often position this group in opposition to a perceived 'elite'. It is frequently associated with anti-establishment and anti-political sentiment. Populism as an ideology that presents "the people" as a morally good force and contrasts them against "the elite", who are portrayed as corrupt and self-serving. Populism is a political movement emphasizing rhetoric phrase or slogans of 'us- versus-them' world view in which the "us" refers to the "people," defined often in ethnic or communal terms and seen as engaged in a zero-sum battle with "them," defined most often as liberal elites, the establishment, and minorities and/or immigrants (Berman, 2020).

To Mendilow (2021) Populism mean a specific political style, discourse frame or strategy, designed to mobilize the deserving majority (the 'people') against, allegedly, corrupt, conspiring elites and the institutions they occupy. According to Diamond (2019), populism has four core features: anti-elitist; anti-institutional; plebiscitary, and ultra-majoritarian. Populism is a political approach or ideology that seeks to represent the interests and voices of "ordinary people" against an elite establishment that is perceived as corrupt, out of touch, or self-serving. The term is often used in political discourse to describe movements, leaders, or parties that emphasize the will of "the people" as a unified group, contrasting it with the interests of privileged elite.

Civilization is a cultural entity. Villages, regions, ethnic groups, nationalities, religious groups, all have distinct cultures with different levels of cultural heterogeneity. A civilization is thus the highest cultural grouping of people and the broadest level of cultural identity people have short of that which distinguishes humans from other species. It is defined both by common objective elements, such as language, history, religion, customs, institutions, and by the subjective self-identification of people.

Clash of Civilizations is a theory proposed by political scientist Samuel P. Huntington in 1993 which posits that future conflicts will not primarily be driven by ideological (e.g., communism vs. capitalism) or economic differences but by cultural and civilizational divides. Huntington (1993) defines civilizations as the highest cultural groupings of people, differentiated by religion, history, language, and cultural values. He contends that these differences are deep-seated and less mutable than political or economic systems. Huntington argues that in the post-Cold War era, cultural and civilizational differences, rather than ideological or economic conflicts, would be the primary source of global tensions and conflicts.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In order to provide a rational basis for explaining and interpreting; the results of this paper, and also to appraise the main argument of the paper, Huntington's Theory of Clash of Civilizations propounded by Samuel P. Huntington in 1993 and Expanded in his 1996 book "The Clash of Civilizations and the Remaking of World Order" was employed. The central argument in this theory is that future conflicts will primarily arise not along ideological or economic lines, but between cultural and civilizational fault lines. Huntington (1993) argues that as global interactions and communications increase, cultural and religious identities will become the primary sources of conflict. Specifically, he predicts that clashes will occur between the West, Islam, Confucianism, Hinduism, and other major civilizations, with tensions exacerbated by the globalization of culture and ideas.

From the foregoing, we can deduce that, Huntington's theory of the Clash of Civilizations centres on the idea that future global conflicts will be shaped by deep-rooted cultural and civilizational differences, especially as globalization intensify. These conflicts as opined by Huntington (1993) will not primarily be ideological or economic but will instead arise from the confrontation of distinct civilizations, particularly the West, Islam, and Confucianism. Huntington's arguments underscore the belief that cultural identity is the most important factor in shaping global political dynamics and that the clash of civilizations will define the future of global conflict.

In conclusion therefore, although the arguments of Huntington's Clash of Civilizations Theory have been critiqued for oversimplifying global complexities, underplaying the role of economic and political factors, promoting cultural determinism, and potentially fostering division, but its real value cannot be denied. In other words, in spite of the critique, the theory is adopted in this paper for the simple fact that it will help to raise the understanding that populist movements with their strong emphasis on nationalism, cultural identity, and religious values, align closely with Huntington's argument that global conflict in the modern era will be driven by civilizational differences.

POPULISM: AN OVERVIEW OF ITS ORIGIN AND DEVELOPMENT

Two broad explanations were put forward by scholars and commentators on the debate about the origins of populism. These two explanations are the "Demand-Side Explanation" and "Supply-Side Explanations".

Demand-Side Explanation

The Demand-Side Explanation refers to arguments that locate the main cause of populism in the changing grievances or demands of citizens. Demand-side explanations could thus also be considered bottom-up explanations, since they focus on society or individuals in their analyses of populism. Berman (2020) pointed that within the Demand-Side Explanation Camp, a division exists between scholars prioritizing economic demands (Economic Grievance-Based Explanations) and those foregrounding Sociocultural Demands in their explanations of populism (Sociocultural Grievance-Based Explanations).

According to Berman (2020) the Economic Grievance-Based Explanations focuses on how globalization, neoliberalism, technological change, and so on have generated discontent and divisions among citizens by making life more insecure for the working and middle classes and privileging already highly-educated, urban dwellers over less-educated and rural ones. Buttressing Berman's submission, Cramer (2016); Iversen and Soskice (2019) and Jucis (2018) argued that economic developments have created deep divisions within many societies between rich and poor, elites and average people, rural and urban areas, the highly and less educated, etc.. Milanovic (2019) further opined that in addition to creating divisions within societies, economic development has also created deep divisions between countries, since it is not only certain group: in the developed world that have disproportionately benefited from divisions over the past decades but also developing countries, particularly China. According to Milanovic (2016) economic "losers" in the developed world thus blame countries such as China as well as the "winners" within their own societies for their and their countries' problems.

The Sociocultural Grievance-Based Explanations on the other hand, argued that social and cultural trends over the past decades are the main cause of populism. In other words, rather than focusing on economic trends, these types of explanations (Sociocultural Grievance-Based Explanations) argued that social and cultural trends over the past decades (most notably raising immigration, the decline) of traditional values, and the mobilization of women and minority groups) are the main cause of populism. Such trends as pointed out by Berman (2020) have challenged ethnic and gender hierarchies, generating a counter-reaction particularly among white men, the counter-reaction has led to support for the populists politicians, who promise to defend their interests. Buttressing this submission Berman (2020) pointed out that numerous political scientists and political psychologists have documented the power and pervasiveness of group-based identity threats and how they can lead voters to support politicians and parties that promise to protect their group's status and identity.

From the above submissions therefore, one would be right to argue that the recent proliferations of populism and populist movement in U.S in particular is associated with the growing perceived fear by white Americans that they would soon be a minority. Consequently this perceived fear as opined by Craig and Richeson (2014) increases their propensity to favour their own group and become wary of those outside it.

Supply-Side Explanations

Contrary to the Demand-Side Explanation, Supply-Side Explanations reject the view of politics was built into demand-side explanations (i.e., the assumption that broad economic and/or social trends directly or straightforwardly influence citizens' political demands and choices). Instead, supply-side explanations draw on the insights of institutionalist scholars and argue that economic, social, and other structural trends are filtered through institutions that determine how they are translated into political outcomes (Hall and Taylor 1986 in Berman, 2020). In other words, Supply-side explanations, pinpoint the main cause of populism in the decline of responsiveness and effectiveness of political institutions, which has made many citizens willing to vote for politicians and parties with anti-establishment, anti-status quo messages. These types of explanations have become popular in

recent years among scholars of the advanced industrial world, but they have a long history among students of the developing world.

From the above submission therefore, one can argue that the Supply-side explanations, locate the main cause of populism in changes in the nature of democracy itself, in particular the growing inability or unwillingness of elites and institutions to supply responses to citizens demands. Supply-side explanations as opined by Berman (2020) could be considered top-down explanations, since they focus on the failures of governments, politicians, policy makers, parties, and other actors in their analyses of populism. Some scholars of populism focus their attention on the supply side of politics, trying to understand why democratic institutions have become less responsive to citizens, less able to deal with societies' problems over time, and hence inclined to populism or populist ideologist.

Types of Populism

Three types of populism have been identified by scholars in the existing literature and they include:

- i. **Left-Wing Populism:** This is a type of populism which focuses on economic inequality and social justice, often opposing corporate elites and advocating for wealth redistribution. Examples include movements led by figures like Bernie Sanders in the U.S. or Evo Morales in Bolivia.
- ii. **Right-Wing Populism:** This is a type of populism which emphasizes national identity, cultural preservation, and opposition to immigration, often targeting liberal elites or international institutions. Examples include leaders like Donald Trump in the U.S., Viktor Orban in Hungary, or Marine Le Pen in France.
- iii. **Centrist or Reformist Populism:** This is a type of populism which seeks to address perceived corruption or inefficiency in governance without a strong ideological bent.

Examples include certain anti-corruption movements.

POPULISM AND THE POSTULATIONS OF CLASH OF CIVILIZATION: THE NEXUS

It is undeniable fact that, a dialectical relationship exists between "Populism" and "Clash of Civilizations", particularly in the context of how populist movements often frame their political rhetoric and identity. As opined by Berman (2020), Karlson (2024) and Mueller (2019), Populism, which tends to emphasize a division between "the people" and "the elites," can intersect with Clash of Civilizations in the following ways:

- i. Populism or Populist movements often operate through strong appeals to national identity, cultural preservation, and a return to traditional values, emphasizing the "us vs., them" dynamic. This is a central component of populist rhetoric, which often portrays the "elite" or "outsiders" (such as immigrants or foreign political influences) as threats to of national or cultural purity. In this context therefore, populist movements amplify the distinctions between civilizations by framing cultural identity as a key national asset that must be protected. This aligns with Huntington's view that civilizations, when in close proximity, will develop tensions based on their differing values, practices, and historical experiences. For example, populist leaders in Europe often emphasize the threat posed by Muslim immigration, positioning Western civilization's values (such as secularism or Christianity) against what is perceived as the threat of Islamic values, a theme that echoes Huntington's prediction of conflict between the West and Islam.
- ii. Populism often emphasizes nationalism, which in turn fosters a sense of civilizational defense against external or foreign influences. Huntington's theory argues that civilizations are defined by shared cultural, religious, and historical characteristics, and when these characteristics are perceived to be under threat, civilizational identities become more pronounced.
- iii. Populist leaders frequently use rhetoric about cultural and national sovereignty, presenting their nations as guardians of a specific civilizational identity. For example, in Hungary, Prime Minister Viktor Orban has championed an "illiberal democracy" and framed the defense of Hungarian cultural and Christian values as crucial to the survival of Hungary's national identity. This also aligns with Huntington's argument that the West will increasingly view itself as being in opposition to civilizations that pose a cultural or religious threat, particularly the Islamic and Confucian civilizations. Populism, by placing a strong emphasis on the preservation of cultural homogeneity, may inadvertently deepen these civilizational divides by positioning national identities as incompatible with foreign or immigrant cultures.
- iv. Huntington argues that religion is a central feature of civilizations and a major source of conflict. Populist movements often use religious identity as a central theme in their politics, especially in regions where religion is tightly intertwined with cultural identity. In Europe, for instance, populist leaders often frame Muslim immigrants not only as a threat to national sovereignty but also as a challenge to the Christian foundations of European civilization. In the United States, Donald Trump's rhetoric about "protecting American values" often includes appeals to Christian ideals, reinforcing a civilizational divide between the Western (Christian) world and non-Western, particularly Muslim, civilizations. Thus, the emphasis on religious identity in populist politics reinforces Huntington's idea that cultural and religious distinctions will become a primary source of conflict. This is because populism accelerates this by presenting these differences (cultural and religious distinctions) in stark; confrontational terms, potentially inflaming tensions between civilizations.

HOW POPULISM ACCENTUATE THE PROSPECT OF CLASH OF CIVILIZATION IN CONTEMPORARY GLOBAL POLITICS

From the foregoing premises, it clear that populism have accentuated the prospects of a "clash of civilizations" in contemporary global politics in several ways, often by exacerbating cultural and identity-based divisions within and between nations. But for the purpose of this paper, the following are some key mechanisms through which populism amplified the accentuation of clash of civilization in contemporary global politics as identified by Berman (2020), Karlson (2024) and Mueller (2019):

- i. Populist movements frequently emphasize the protection of national identity, often in opposition to foreign influence, immigration, or multiculturalism. These emphases on "us vs. them" have led to heightened tensions between different cultural or religious groups, both domestically and internationally. By focusing on cultural purity or traditional values, populist leaders have stoked fears of cultural erosion, creating an environment ripe for conflict between civilizations.
- ii. Populist rhetoric often includes scepticism or rejection of globalization, viewing it as a force that undermines national sovereignty and cultural identity. This stance can contribute to a dichotomy between Western, globalized, and non-western civilizations, reinforcing a perception that Western values are being threatened by other civilizations, particularly those with different religious or cultural frameworks.
- iii. Many populist movements in the West have capitalized on fears related to immigration, particularly from Muslim-majority countries. By framing the influx of immigrants as an existential threat to national values and security, populism can foster a perception of a cultural clash between the West and Islamic civilizations, reinforcing a binary opposition that may escalate tensions and contribute to an adversarial' clash."
- iv. Populist leaders often invoke historical grievances or narratives that emphasize past conflicts between civilizations (e.g., the Crusades, the Cold War, colonialism). These narratives can serve to rally people around a shared sense of victimhood or cultural superiority, further entrenching a mind-set of inevitable clash rather than cooperation.
- v. Populism tends to create a highly polarized political climate, in which moderate voices and nuanced dialogue are drowned out. In such an environment, civilizational differences are often amplified, and compromise or coexistence becomes more difficult. As populist rhetoric hardens, it can create a feedback loop in which perceived cultural conflicts are portrayed as intractable, increasing the likelihood of real-world tensions.
- vi. Populist leaders may adopt authoritarian policies aimed at curbing foreign influence and enforcing cultural norms. These policies can include limiting religious or cultural practices deemed "alien" and curtailing freedoms for minorities. Such measures can exacerbate divisions within society, fostering resentment from groups seen as outsiders and reinforcing the idea of an inevitable clash between civilizations.

From the foregoing submission therefore, populism, through its emphasis on nationalism, anti-globalization, cultural protectionism, and often exclusionary rhetoric, can contribute to a heightened sense of a "clash of civilizations" by fostering division and tension both within and between cultures.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

It is deducible from the foregoing analysis that the interplay between populism and the Clash of Civilizations thesis reveals a complex and mutually reinforcing dynamic that shapes contemporary global politics. Populism, with its reliance on this dichotomy of "the people" versus "the elite," often amplifies cultural and civilizational fault lines by appealing to identity-based grievances and exclusionary rhetoric. When populist movements draw upon civilizational narratives, they create fertile ground for conflicts that align with Samuel Huntington's predictions, wherein cultural differences become the primary sources of global tension. In other words, the paper established that a dialectical relationship exists between "Populism" and "Clash of Civilizations", particularly in the context of how populist movements often frame their political rhetoric and identity which tends to emphasize a division between "the people" and "the elites," can intersect with Huntington's theory in several ways.

However, while populism accentuates the prospects of a clash of civilizations, it is important to note that numerous crises in global politics demonstrate the limitations of a civilizational framework. This is for the fact that, many of these conflicts are driven by political, economic, historical, and identity-based factors that transcend cultural or religious lines. A good example is the Iraq War of 2003 which was product of geopolitical and resource interests, especially related to oil and regional power dynamics, rather than a clear civilizational conflict. The U.S.-led invasion was justified on the grounds of eliminating weapons of mass destruction and promoting democracy, rather than any supposed cultural or religious clash with Islam. Additionally, the involvement of various religious sects (Shiite, Sunni, and Kurdish) within Iraq further complicates any simple civilizational framework. Another example was the activities of some international terrorist group such Al-Qaeda, ISIS. This is because, while groups like al-Qaeda and ISIS use religion as a rallying cry, their actions are driven by a complex mixture of radical political ideology, anti-colonial sentiment, and regional power struggles rather than a simple clash of civilizations.

In conclusion, it is undisputable fact the rise of populism serves as both a reflection of and a catalyst for the tensions predicted by the Clash of Civilizations thesis. It amplifies civilizational divides by fostering exclusionary identities and antagonistic rhetoric,

heightening the risk of cultural and geopolitical conflicts. To counter these dynamics, the following recommendations are hereby offered to guide those in position of leadership at all levels.

- i. Governments and leaders should prioritize inclusive governance that addresses the concerns of diverse groups within their societies. Political discourse should emphasize commonalities and shared values rather than highlighting divisive civilizational or cultural narratives. Initiatives like inclusive policymaking and bipartisan cooperation can counter populist tendencies to polarize.
- ii. Efforts must focus on addressing the root causes of populist discontent, such as economic inequality, unemployment, political corruption, and lack of access to education. Equitable policies that bridge the socioeconomic gap and improve the list in democratic institutions can reduce the appeal of populist leaders who exploit grievances for political gain.
- iii. Teaching students about the interconnectedness of civilizations, shared histories, and the dangers of stereotyping can help dismantle the narratives on inevitable conflict.

REFERENCES

- 1) Berman, S (2020) The Causes of Populism in the West, Annual Review of Political Science, available at polisci.annualreviews.org
- 2) Craig MA, Richeson JA. (2014) More diverse yet less tolerant? How the increasingly diverse racial landscape affects white Americans' racial attitudes. *Personal. Soc. Psychol. Bull.* 40(6):750–61
- 3) De-Cueto-Nogueras, C (2018) Right Wing Populism in Europe: A Discursive Rhetoric Focused on European Union, Ethno-Nationalism, Democracy and Globalization, https://www.ritsumei.ac.jp/acd/re/k-rsc/hss/book/pdf/no116_04.pdf, pp. 369 – 400
- 4) Diamond, L. (2019). *Ill winds: Saving democracy from Russian rage, Chinese ambition, and American complacency.* Penguin Press.
- 5) Hall P, Taylor R. 1986. Political science and the three new institutionalisms, in Berman, S (2020) The Causes of Populism in the West, Annual Review of Political Science, available at polisci.annualreviews.org
- 6) Huntington, S. P. (1993). "The Clash of Civilizations?" *Foreign Affairs*, 72(3), 22-49, available at <https://www.foreignaffairs.com>
- 7) Huntington, Samuel P. (1996). *The Clash of Civilizations and the Remaking of World Order.* New York: Simon & Schuster.
- 8) Karlson, N (2024) 'Populism: Defining Characteristics' in *Reviving Classical Liberalism Against Populism*, Palgrave Studies in Classical Liberalism, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-49074-3_2
- 9) Løland, OJ. (2020) The Political Conditions and Theological Foundations of the New Christian Right in Brazil. *Iberoamericana – Nordic Journal of Latin American and Caribbean Studies*, 49(1): pp. 63–73. Available at <https://www.duo.uio.no/bitstream/handle/10852/81103/2/IberoamericanaBrazil.pdf>
- 10) Mendilow, J (2021) Introduction to Populism and Corruption in Jonathan Mendilow and Éric Phélippeau (eds.) (2021) *Populism and Corruption*, Edward Elgar Publishing Limited The Lypiatts 15 Lansdown Road Cheltenham Glos GL50 2JA UK
- 11) Milanovic B. (2019) *Capitalism, Alone: The Future of the System that Rules the World.* Cambridge, MA: Harvard Univ. Press
- 12) Mueller, A (2019) 'The meaning of 'populism'', *Philosophy and Social Criticism*, 45 (9-10) 1025–1057, available at sagepub.com/journals-permissions
- 13) Santana, C.H.V and Ferrario, M.N (2022) Middle Classes and the Rise of Authoritarian Populist Rulers: a comparison between contemporary Brazil and India, Paper Delivered at the 2022 Virtual Congress of the Latin American Studies Association (LASA) May 5-8, available at https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Carlos-Santana-4/publication/360443817_Middle_Classes_and_the_Rise_of_Authoritarian_Populist_Rulers_a_comparison_between_contemporary_Brazil_and_India/links/6276689b107cae2919918ae1/Middle-Classes-and-the-Rise-of-Authoritarian-Populist-Rulers-a-comparison-between-contemporary-Brazil-and-India.pdf